

Metadata for Reuse: What Does That Mean?

A Case Study

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Abstract. We present a current development effort to create an ontology to describe observational targets in planetary science data. This is part of a larger effort to support and encourage the discovery and reuse of the unique data sets comprising the holdings of the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) by the next generations of planetary researchers.

1. Introduction

The Planetary Data System (PDS) is the designated archive receiving all science data returned by, gathered in support of, and closely associated with NASA's planetary exploration missions and data analysis programs. When the PDS was created over 30 years ago, the reuse of data followed much the same paradigm as reuse of published literature: An interested researcher would select a data set based on a text description in a catalog; request a (initially physical, later digital) copy of the complete data set and any accompanying documentation; and was then largely on their own for determining how to apply the data to the task at hand.

In the intervening decades, space exploration has become an international and often multi-national endeavor, and the holdings of PDS and its sibling archives around the globe continue to increase by orders of magnitude every few years. The amount of data available for reuse is now well beyond the ability of any one researcher to encompass in its entirety, and the old paradigm of reuse is inadequate to the modern task. Instead, researchers need software tools to support finding data as well as manipulating them. In turn, these tools must be supported by the archival data – specifically by the metadata recorded and made available by the curating archive. These metadata need to be programmatically actionable – that is, programming logic needs to be able to use the metadata to make decisions without constant human interaction.

The fundamental problem, of course, is that no software can act on metadata that do not exist. The challenge that PDS and similar archives face is gathering metadata in a programmatically actionable form that does not preclude entire classes of reuse *a priori*.

2. What is “Reuse”?

For the purposes of this discussion, we define two categories of “reuse”: *complementary* and *novel*. We will focus on the latter.

2.1. Complementary Reuse

Complementary reuse includes reproducing/replicating original results, correlative analysis, creation of higher-order products by combining data sets with similar coverage, and any activities closely aligned with the science objectives of the original experiment(s). So, for example, a data set of spectral measurements of rocks on the surface of Mars might be

compared to spectra of meteorite samples; a series of images of the lunar surface might be combined with spectral data and laser ranging to produce an analysis-ready data set for Geospatial Information System (GIS) application; etc.

Complementary reuse is typically well-supported by the metadata supplied with the data set submission to the curating archive. Since it is closely aligned with the original experimental objectives, the metadata describing the relevant observational parameters and data reductions are usually very complete. Part of the PDS intake process, for example, is holding an external peer review of the data and metadata to ensure completeness and usability for complementary applications.

Users looking for data for complementary reuse often know that the data they are looking for exist. They may even know fairly specifically where to find them. Even in cases where the user is looking for similar results from unknown sources, if their search returns no results, they are fairly confident that additional data do not exist. This advantage in findability for complementary reuse stems from the metadata, of course. The discipline-specific metadata used to describe the data contain the terms used by the discipline community to classify, and thus search, for data.

2.2 Novel Reuse

Novel reuse includes any and every use of the data (or metadata) that is *not* aligned with the original objectives of the experiment. This includes the relatively common case of going back to older data to find observations supporting a current discovery – the active volcanism recently discovered in Magellan mission data (Herrick and Hensley, 2023) being an excellent example. Converting shape models of small bodies and planetary surface features into 3D-printable files is also a novel reuse that has become a standard and popular practice within some nodes of the PDS.

Metadata to support novel reuse are, perforce, more difficult to define and less likely to exist precisely because the potential applications are unknown and even unimaginable to the data producer and archival curators at the time the metadata are developed. The discipline-specific metadata that support complementary reuse so well may rely on discipline-specific jargon, or may fail to record parameters that are considered either obvious or irrelevant to the original analysis. Relationships that are obvious in the context of the original investigation may not be explicitly detailed in the metadata, making them invisible to novel searches. Finally, even when the relevant metadata are recorded, if they are not indexed or exposed for search through the archive interfaces, they cannot be used to find or select data.

The novel reuse of data sets – applications that fork away from the original scientific goals or support entirely different fields of research – provides an additional, unanticipated return on investment that can only be realized if the metadata are available and actionable.

3. Novel Reuse: An Example

Hale, et al. (2017) is an example of a novel reuse of metadata from ground-based observatories. Their study looks at the variation in atmospheric extinction coefficient over time at several solar observatories that have been in operation for 20 years or more. Extinction coefficients are used

to remove the effects of the atmosphere from observations of stars and, in this case, the Sun, made from observatories located within the Earth's atmosphere. The coefficients vary with the angle of observation through the atmosphere and observatory location as well as transitory effects like season, weather, and upper atmosphere contamination from major events like volcanic eruptions.

The purpose of the study was to analyze variation over time in the morning and afternoon extinction coefficients in order to improve the calibration of data from the specific solar observatories in the BiSON network. Figure 3 of that paper shows a marked increase in extinction coefficients at Observatorio del Teide, located on Tenerife in the Canary Islands, in 1991 following the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo in the Philippines, and even a hint of long-term effects from the 1982 eruption of El Chichón (Mexico). Similar effects can be seen in extinction coefficient graphs from other observatories.

From this example, it is possible to imagine a broader study that utilizes historic extinction coefficient data from ground-based observatories to track the long-term effects of volcanic eruptions on particulates in various levels of the atmosphere. Such a study would be entirely focused on metadata, specifically the date, pointing, wavelength observed, and calculated extinction coefficients. The original target of the observation would not be relevant to such a novel application. If the extinction metadata are not programmatically accessible, however, the researcher's ability to exploit these metadata would be seriously hindered.

4. Case Study: Targeting in the PDS Archive

Being able to find observations based on the target of those observations is one of the most requested searches executed on PDS data, and also one of the more difficult to support even for complementary research. Novel research based on target of observation is particularly difficult to support. Decades ago, the question "What is the target of the observation?" typically had simple answers, like "Mars", "the Moon", or "Jupiter". As solar system exploration has matured, however, we now have spacecraft orbiting planetary targets for months or years at a time as well as surface-landing laboratories and rovers contributing to the wealth of planetary data available in the PDS. The question "What is the target of observation?" no longer has a simple answer. Some examples will illustrate the complexities that abound in modern remote sensing missions.

4.1 Some Examples

Figure 1 shows two images taken by the Ingenuity helicopter that arrived on Mars with the Perseverance rover. The image on the left shows the wreckage from the spacecraft that brought the rover and helicopter to the surface of Mars. The image on the right shows the helicopter's own shadow below it in flight. Clearly, a target identification of "Mars" does nothing to improve the findability of these distinctive images in the Mars2020 mission archive, while a target of "Wreckage" or "Helicopter Shadow" ignores the context of the image (that is, the Martian surface). Attempting to incorporate the context into the target name string results in values like "Mars2020 Ingenuity Helicopter Shadow, Mars Surface". A value like this relies on the user to guess the terms that will appear in the metadata that might be associated with what

they are looking for and hope the search engine prioritization algorithms will work in their favor.

Figure 1. *The image on the left shows wreckage from the delivery vehicle that carried the Perseverance rover, as imaged by the Ingenuity helicopter (the shadow of which is visible in the bottom center-right). The image on the right is a “selfie” taken by the Ingenuity helicopter of its own shadow while in flight. Image credit: NASA/JPL-Caltech.*

Figure 2 shows two images from the recent planetary defense mission, DART. The image on the left is the last full-frame image returned by the DART spacecraft prior to impacting Dimorphos, the moon of the Didymos system. The image on the right was taken by the companion LICIACube satellite and shows Dimorphos hidden in a cloud of ejecta from the impact. A target search for “Dimorphos” would certainly return the first image, but a simple target search may not return the second if the target identification is “Didymos” or even “Didymos System”.

It is certainly possible to imagine including multiple target identifications in the metadata for a data product. In the Figure 1 case, for example, the metadata might contain a list of targets, including “Shadow”, “Helicopter”, “Wreckage”, “Mars Surface”, and so on. This, however, is not congenial to the typical mission pipeline coded to identify targets based on observation plans and pre-designated targeting. Machine learning or human intervention could teach a search routine that “Dimorphos” is part of the “Didymos” system, but creating training sets or otherwise incorporating associations into searches requires significant additional effort that is not funded for either the data producers or the curating archives. Attempting to generalize either approach threatens to rapidly exhaust available resources.

Figure 2. *The image on the left shows the surface of Dimorphos, the moon in the Didymos system, just prior to the DART mission impact (image credit: NASA/Johns Hopkins APL). The image on the right is from the LICIACube companion satellite and shows the Didymos system shortly after impact, with Dimorphos obscured by the dust cloud raised by the impact (image credit: ASI/NASA).*

Finally, consider the case of a rover that approaches a rock, abrades the surface of that rock, and then does a spectral analysis of the surface revealed. The list of things that might be identified as the target of that observation is fairly long, and includes:

- the inside of the rock
- the rock itself
- the local feature (a crater, a hill, etc.) in which the rock is located
- the region in which the local feature is located
- the planetary body on which the region is located
- the planetary system containing the body

The full context of the observation includes all of these specifications (and potentially a host of others). Which of these things is perceived as the correct answer to “What is the target of the observation?” depends critically on why a user is searching for data in the first place. To complicate matters, the user might be searching for a specific target identification at any of these levels or might be searching for targets of a particular *type* at any of these levels. Consequently, the complete context of an observation, from general to specific, needs to be associated with the resulting data in order to support discoverability and reuse based on target of observation.

4.2 Aspects of the Solution

Clearly the solution to the PDS target description problem is going to involve controlled vocabularies – formally defined taxonomies that can be resolved through unique,

programmatically actionable identifiers – for the *type* of target observed. Few, if any, already exist to describe the various types of targets in the PDS holdings. We expect to have to create type taxonomies to describe observed objects and phenomena like: activity associated with comet nuclei; calibration targets; “selfies” of various bits of hardware; extended phenomena like magnetic and gravitational fields; and so on.

Additionally, our solution needs to incorporate formal identifiers, informal names, and even nicknames used contemporaneously during the life of a mission in order to support discoverability and reuse based on the *identity* of the target observed.

The solution then needs to be incorporated into the formal information model that defines the format, structure, and content of all our archival metadata. This will provide the standardization of terminology and usage that gives a user a measure of confidence in the completeness of the results returned from a search on target of observation.

Finally, we need to do this in a way that makes it possible to enlist the data producers in the task of providing the complete set of context information for each target observed, even when that larger context is obvious to the instrument teams or must describe a situation as complex as those in Figures 1 and 2.

4.3 First Steps

The first essential step toward the solution is the development of the formal taxonomies that will be needed, along with a system to manage them. Multiple taxonomies will be used to divide the problem into specific domains in which relatively simple hierarchical taxonomies can be defined and extended within clear boundaries. These can then be used to build an ontological system for defining context that recognizes the relationships (like “a body that has an atmosphere” or “dust observed in the vicinity of a comet nucleus”) that are potentially important selectors in searches across the entire PDS archive.

To focus the initial development effort, we restricted the scope of the task to targets known to exist at the time of observation and that were intended to be observed. We developed an initial list of less than a dozen high-level domains and began to populate each with a hierarchy of relevant terms. Preliminary results were presented in a poster at the AGU Fall 2022 meeting (Rough, et al. 2022) and generated some fruitful discussions. As a result, we are encouraged to continue down the path to formalization.

5. Conclusion

Archives that curate research data sets provide the means for realizing return on investment in basic research. To do so, however, the research data must be supported by programmatically accessible and actionable metadata. Metadata submitted with research data sets typically provide good support for finding and reuse of the data for additional analyses closely related to the original science objectives. However, the ability to find and reuse the same data sets for novel applications not imagined at the time the data sets were produced can be hindered by contextual metadata not explicitly included because they were not deemed relevant or important by the original producers. In the case of the PDS holdings, describing the target of observation is an aspect of metadata description that is increasingly subject to this sort of

limitation. The solution appears to lie in the development of a broad ontology for describing targeting that incorporates formal domain taxonomies, associations between various types of planetary targets, formal and informal identifiers, and a method to encourage completeness in targeting descriptions at the time of data set creation that has yet to be designed.

6. References

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